

Contributors Guidebook for the Data Observatories and Open Collections

Daniel Antal

2023-12-05

Introduction

Big data creates **inequalities**, because only the world's biggest global corporations, best endowed universities and strongest governments can maintain long, well-designed, global data collection programs.

This handbook is made for people working together in an [open collaboration](#) on the [Digital Music Observatory](#) and its funded projects, [Listen Local Lithuania](#), [Eviota](#), [SurveyHarmonies](#) and [Open Music Europe](#); the connecting [Open Collection Network](#) and the [CCSI Data Observatory](#) and [Green Deal Data Observatory](#).

Get in [epub](#) or [docx](#) formats.

1 Overview

1.1 Ambition in the Open Music Europe Grant Agreement

[Open Music Europe](#) aims to contribute to the aim of creating a decentralised European intelligence hub where centralised data collection and analysis have failed in the music industry during the past 20 years.

We envision the Open Data Observatory as a decentralised, complementary service to the ESSnet system (Eurostat and the national statistics offices) and the planned, centralised European Music Observatory (EMO). [...] We plan to implement the Open Data Observatory as an open-source, public-facing solution working in synergy with the EMO.

We will create reproducible “dynamic policy documents” that can be transferred from one country to another or scaled up from one country to a group of countries or even the entire European Union, and recast with little effort after the inception of new data every year, due to their very high level of data/output standardisation and interoperability.

Instead of creating a large budget, ad-hoc valuation reports, these reports, with their automatic data harvesting and processing, can be recast annually with little further investment, or they can be transferred from Hungary to Bulgaria, from Slovakia to Lithuania.

1.2 Methodology in the Open Music Europe Grant Agreement

The Level 3 version of the *Open Policy Analysis* (OPA) Guidelines gives practical guidance on how to improve the transparency and replicability of policy-making work with a scientific underpinning. The OPA guidelines go farther than current Horizon Europe recommendations, subjecting policy research and deliberation to standards as rigorous as those used in e.g. open-source software development and open science peer review.

The guidelines consist of three layers:

- ☒ open materials (i.e., the evidence considered in policy) | check out the materials of this handbook.
- ☒ open analysis (the analytical procedures to which the evidence is subject); see for example [D 1.3 Report on the European Music Economy](#) | [Slides](#) | [file folder](#) | [long term storage](#) | [README](#).
- ☒ open output (the indicators, recommendations, etc. derived from the analysis): we synchronize them with libraries via [OpenAIRE](#) and our visual assets and cultural data via [Europeana](#) aggregators.

Each level must be fully replicable. Establishing a clear link between input and output by displaying how the output changes under Open Music Europe uses Open Policy Analysis to create policy-relevant indicators. (Hoces de la Guardia, Grant, and Miguel 2020) and they are fully in line with the Open Science objectives of the European Union (Commission et al. 2020).

Figure 1.1: Our ambition to increase transparency with introducing the Open Policy Analysis into the European music policies and collaborative data use in the European industry.

Open Music Europe furthermore ensures that all materials, analysis, and outputs meet the FAIR principles enshrined in Horizon Europe and the EU's open science agenda and will be submitted as best practices to the *Knowledge4Policy* K4P Portal horizontal knowledge areas on Evidence-Informed Policy Making, Composite Indicators, Modelling, and AI Watch.

In Europe, the European Commission launched the platform, along with several initiatives to make EU-funded research more accessible, notably, with changing some financial guidelines for its research program, and amending the [Open Data Directive](#) in 2019.

The subsequent chapters of this Manual show how we will comply with both FAIR and OPA by making our documents and files [Findable](#) in a way that meets open policy analysis compliance, make them [Interoperable](#) for machines and researchers, [Accessible](#) for human and algorithms, and [Reusable](#) for human and automated use.

These efforts toward radical transparency will help ensure open deliberation and consensus-forming among stakeholders. Putting evidence-based policymaking into practice in music research, we will establish a precedent for its incorporation as a keystone of the social sciences and digital humanities more broadly.

1.3 OPA

The [OPA Guidelines](#) feature nine steps for implementation, grouped by their relation to the three key principles of OPA: Open Output, Open Analysis, and Open Materials. Each step is modular, meaning it can be implemented independently from the rest, and features three gradual levels of rigor. Analysts can adopt each step at varying levels of rigor, depending on what is appropriate for their work. Status quo in policy analysis practices should be interpreted as Level 0.

You can become a signatory of the OPA Guidelines by adding your name (or the name of your organization, if you sign as an organizational representative) to [this form](#) and including a statement in policy reports indicating they were developed in accordance with the OPA Guidelines (e.g., “This analysis complies with level 3 of the Open Policy Analysis (OPA) Guidelines developed by BITSS”). Second, you can submit your feedback to these Guidelines to [BITSS Project](#).

1.4 Documents, Word Processing, Manuscripts, Blogposts

We must make our documents Findable, Interoperable, Accessible and Reusable. We introduce the [tidy text](#) concept in the [Interoperability](#) chapter.

Interoperability in this case making your text editing simpler. Regardless your use of Word, Grammarly, Libre, or a markdown editor, we would like you to keep it as simple that it can be translated to markdown notation, which then can create automatically correct, beautiful Word, PDF, or LaTeX documents.

Markdown is a very simple text notation, similar to the earlier manuscript markup languages used by book editors. You can learn it in 1-2 hours, but even if you do not use it, you should always check that your formatting remains simple enough to be translated (simplified) to markdown. An introduction to using markdown is in 9 [Tidy Text](#). You can get the concept in 10 minutes with [Dillinger](#).

See the first version of our slide templates [here](#), and visit our template folder ([Open Music Europe dissemination and communications assets](#)). Help our colleagues at Synyo to make

this template more aesthetic, more usable, and more interoperable by sending issues and big reports [here](#).

1.5 Datasets, Tables, Tabular Data

We must make our documents Findable, Interoperable, Accessible and Reusable. We introduce the [tidy data](#) concept in the [Interoperability](#) chapter, and go into further depth (only to be used for the Data Management Plan, and some quantitative task of WP1, WP2, WP3, and the programming parts of WP3) in the 5.1 [Tidy data](#) separate chapter.

For laypersons, tidy data ensures that your data is very easy to import into a relational database (SQL, etc) or it can be read into Excel, OpenOffice, SPSS or STATA without a hiss. Keeping your data is keeping your data simple, and will save you countless hours in the [Data Sisyphus](#).

1.6 Presentations

Presentations are special types of documents where the visual elements dominate. Making them truly interoperable is a big challenge, because we expect them to work on a projector, on a Windows laptop, an Apple desktop, a Linux server, on a tablet, smartphone.

See the first version of our slide templates [here](#), and visit our template folder ([Open Music Europe dissemination and communications assets](#)). Help our colleagues at Synyo to make this template more aesthetic, more usable, and more interoperable by sending issues and big reports [here](#).

1.7 Working Folders (repositories)

Our file folders, or repositories, are stored on Microsoft's Github. They work similarly to a Google Drive or a Dropbox, but with some further features that makes them compliant with the EU's FAIR and the OPA.

The use of a standardised file structure and the use of an open, selfcontained folder with a readme file is central to 7 [Open collaboration](#), i.e., or project management philosophy, as well as to compliance with the 3 F - [Findable](#) principle in the European open science requirements and in OPA.

- Access to them is not proprietary, it requires the https protocol (or SSH)
- They are version controlled, and protected for deleting, overwriting
- Many people can work on them without disturbing each other.
- WP leaders and task leaders can assign tasks connected to files (such as issues, check out the improvement issues to make our Word and PPTX files truly interoperable).
- Competing ideas can be discussed under the issues, or help can be asked for, even outside of our work groups or consortia.
- You need a program to sync it to your computer (Similarly to DropBox or Microsoft's OneDrive)

The downside is a bit more learning:

- You do not work in the same folder, like in Google Drive, in the cloud, you always create your copy ('fork') first, so that you are protected from accidentally overwriting; this is both a blessing and a curse for beginners.
- The sync is never automatic: you always have to approve every download and upload
- Resolving conflicts (you changed something in a text that somebody else also changed in a different way) requires experience.

You find more information on how to use Git and GitHub in the [Collaboration tools](#) chapter.

1.8 Final folders for synchronization and publication

Our long term storage is [Zenodo](#), the repository system of [OpenAIRE](#) and CERN, the European Organization for Nuclear Research.

Zenodo is an extremely useful tool: - [x] It places our work directly into global library catalogues, if it is high-enough capacity - [x] It connects it to people who cite us, it connects it with similar books, articles, datasets - [x] It provides for a truly open and interoperable access point.

Yet, it is no exception to the garbage-in-garbage-out principle. In WP4 we develop tools that help to make out a lot more from your blogposts, presentations, manuscripts, final articles, and datasets on Zenodo and the global knowledge graphs. See more in 5.1 [Tidy data](#).

Check out our

[Digital Music Observatory collection](#) and this particular [storage folder](#).

1.9 Biographies

We use [ORCID](#) because we rely on Zenodo as an open source repository, but we can include almost any academic badge on your profile that you like, just make sure that you have an ORCID ID, too.

1.10 Photographs

2 Inspiration

To become a data curator, you do not need to be a data scientist, a statistician, or a data engineer. We are looking for professionals, researchers, or citizen scientists who are interested in data and its visualisation and its potential to form the basis of informed business or policy decisions and to provide scientific or legal evidence. Our ideal curators share a passion for data-driven evidence or visualisations and have a strong, subjective idea about the data that would inform them in their work.

2.1 We need data

2.1.1 No Data is Available: This Scientist Stung Himself With Dozens Of Insects Because No One Else Would

The Schmidt Pain Index, as its informally known, runs from 1-4. The common honey bee serves as its anchor point, a solid 2. At the top end of the scale lie the bullet ant and the tarantula hawk (which is neither a tarantula nor a hawk; it's a wasp). Watch the video with Dr. Schmidt, and listen to the whole interview [here](#). [This Scientist Stung Himself With Dozens Of Insects Because No One Else Would](#).

2.1.2 Nobody Counted Them Before: Big Data Is Saving This Little Bird

“We need to improve conservation by improving wildlife monitoring. Counting plants and animals is really tricky business.” [Big Data Is Saving This Little Bird](#)

2.2 From Datasets and Files to Living Web Resources {web-30}

2.2.1 Web 3.0

2.3 Remain Critical: Ethical Data, Trustworthy AI

Sometimes we put our hands on data that looks like a unique starting point to create a new indicator. But our indicator will be flawed if the original dataset is flawed. And it can be flawed in many ways, most likely that some important aspect of the information was omitted, or the data is autoselected, for example, under-sampling women, people of colour, or observations from small or less developed countries.

2.3.1 Machine Learning from Bad Data: Weapons of Math Destruction, Algorithms of Oppression

Cathy O'Neil: [Weapons of math destruction](https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/roots-of-unity/review-weapons-of-math-destruction/), which O'Neil are mathematical models or algorithms that claim to quantify important traits: teacher quality, recidivism risk, creditworthiness but have harmful outcomes and often reinforce inequality, keeping the poor poor and the rich rich. They have three things in common: opacity, scale, and damage. <https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/roots-of-unity/review-weapons-of-math-destruction/>(<https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/roots-of-unity/review-weapons-of-math-destruction/>)

In [Algorithms of Oppression](#), Safiya Umoja Noble challenges the idea that search engines like Google offer an equal playing field for all forms of ideas, identities, and activities. Data discrimination is a real social problem; Noble argues that the combination of private interests in promoting certain sites, along with the monopoly status of a relatively small number of Internet search engines, leads to a biased set of search algorithms that privilege whiteness and discriminate against people of colour, especially women of colour.

2.3.2 Big Data Creates Inequalities: Data Feminism

Catherine D'Ignazio and Lauren F. Klein: [Data Feminism](#). This is a much-celebrated book and with a good reason. It views AI and data problems from a feminist point of view, but the examples and the toolbox can be easily imagined for small-country biases, racial, ethnic, or small enterprise problems. A very good introduction to the injustice of big data and the fight for a fairer use of data, and how bad data collection practices through garbage in-garbage out lead to misleading information or even misinformation.

2.3.3 Bad Data collection Used for Modeling: Why The Bronx Burned

[Why The Bronx Burned](#). Between 1970 and 1980, seven census tracts in the Bronx lost more than 97 percent of their buildings to fire and abandonment. In his book [The Fires](#), Joe Flood blames the misguided “best and brightest” effort by New York City to increase government efficiency. With the help of the Rand Corp., the city tried to measure fire response times, identify redundancies in service, and close or re-allocate fire stations accordingly. What resulted, though, was a perfect storm of bad data: The methodology was flawed, the analysis was rife with biases, and the results were interpreted in a way that stacked the deck against poorer neighbourhoods. The slower response times allowed smaller fires to rage uncontrolled in the city’s most vulnerable communities. Listen to the podcast [here](#).

2.3.4 Bad Incentives Are Blocking Better Science

[Bad Incentives Are Blocking Better Science](#) “There’s a difference between an answer and a result. But all the incentives are pointing toward telling you that as soon as you get a result, you stop.” After the deluge of retractions, the stories of fraudsters, the false positives, and the high-profile failures to replicate landmark studies, some people have begun to ask: “[Is science broken?](#)”. Listen to the pdocast [[Science is Hard](#)] (<https://podcasts.apple.com/us/podcast/10-science-is-hard/id1011406983?i=1000391467935>)

2.4 Reality Check

2.4.1 Looking Behind Data: Moving to America’s Worst Place to Live

Christopher Ingraham wrote [a quick blog post](#) for The Washington Post about an obscure USDA data set called the `natural_amenities_index`, which attempts to quantify the natural beauty of different parts of the country. He described the rankings, noted the counties at the top and bottom, hit publish and did not think much of it. Almost immediately, he started to hear from the residents of northern Minnesota, who were not very happy that Chris had written, “The absolute worst place to live in America is (drumroll, please) ... Red Lake County, Minn.” He could not have been more wrong ... a year later [he moved](#) to Red Lake County with his family.

3 F - Findable

The first step in (re)using data, text, sound recordings, films, photographs is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers.

Making datasets, texts, photos, sound recordings (together: digital assets) easier to find is the first step to higher visibility, higher impact; it avoids unnecessary costs.

We want to make our digital assets findable for both humans and computers (search engines, recommender systems.) You do not need to be a librarian, an archivist or web programmer to make this happen, but it requires a certain discipline in your workflows to make your assets findable. We want to make this process practical and painless.

3.1 Think about your computer as if it was the internet

What makes something easy to find on the Internet?

3.2 Place the digital asset to the right place

The simplest metadata, which is all so often used in our automated positions is to use the file location as information about what the file is. Is it placed in the `assets/img/` folder: it is an image asset. Is it in the `content/event/` folder: it contains date, time, venue location and information about an event.

3.3 Use meaningful names

There are only two hard things in Computer Science: cache invalidation and naming things. – Phil Karlton

Meaningful variable names (in a file), meaningful headings (which will be part of a table of contents or catalogue) and meaningful filenames are absolutely important to findability, interoperability and reusability.

Using systematic names is hard. It is very hard. We can only try to improve. Here are a few tips:

- ☒ Use a clear system: avoid UpperCase letters, space, and non-ASCII characters.
- ☒ Instead of the `,` use `_` underscore or `-` short hyphen in a systematic way.

Good file names with a path to their location contain plenty of easy to read, easy to understand metadata.

`assets/img/blogposts_2023/my_favorite_playlist.png` makes it clear that this is an image (visual) asset illustrating your favorite playlist, and it was published in a 2023 blogpost.

`content/event/2023-03-08_listen-local-lithuania` makes it clear that we find venue information, time, photos, texts about a dissemination event that took place on 2023-03-08.

The trick is that our automated dissemination system turns this information into a website. /event/2023-03-08_listen-local-lithuania/ becomes part of a URL, so that everybody can find this information in the whole wide world.

- Avoid the use of <space>. Space will be translated in URLs to %20, making Listen Local Lithuania Listen%20Local%20Lithuania, which is difficult to read.
- Avoid the use of national characters. Some browsers can read the Veronika Povilionienė character well, others not. Some users have Lithuanian characters, others don't. https://lithuania.listen-local.net/musicians/veronika_povilioniene/ makes it clear that we find information (a file) about Veronika Povilionienė here. It is the very same file on our GitHub source repository (you can add more information about here there), and in the local copy on your computer (if you forked and downloaded it.)
- Avoid the use of space, again. Most of our work is done with program codes (automated), and programming languages treat the <space> in a special way. Variable names cannot contain space in R or Python or any language.

3.4 OPA Requirements

We adhere to the Open Policy Analysis Guidelines, which aim to make your policy-related research findable to everybody in the world, not only you or your supervisor.

Standardise the file structure so that materials are organized in a way that is accessible to an informed reader: all project components are organized in a selfcontained folder using a Standard File Structure (SFS), and a readme file is included.

Our [Report on the European Music Economy](#) is being prepared from the grant proposal stage in this format.

- All the files are placed [into a public repository](#). Anybody can find the files here, and suggest additions, deletions or modifications.
- The repository has a public [readme](#) file. (in text view, [here](#).)

Label and document each input, including data, research, and guesswork: list all inputs, and their sources, and provide links or detailed references. In practice, all our inputs are uploaded into the repositories, and they have included in the standard bibliography (.bib) files which make their citation automatic in use.

Use a version control strategy: All team members use version control software and track changes in a shared project repository. All our deliverables are delivered in a version-controlled repository.

We use Git technology (and Microsoft's GitHub), because it offers version control for even larger groups of people.

- Shared repositories with Git technology offer version control, history, conflict resolution that works on all Windows, Mac, Unix systems.
- Google Drive and Dropbox do not offer version control and conflict resolution.
- Microsoft's SharePoint offers such solutions, but it requires costly licenses and oversight, and do not work outside of the Microsoft universe.

3.5 European Open Science Requirements (non-technical)

Before turning to the European FAIR requirements on Findability, we explain them in lay terms. While the Horizon Europe program requires full compliance with this European Open Science Cloud requirement, for most researchers and innovators it is too technical to follow.

We use globally unique and persistent identifiers: There are many bands called RAIN, many Lithuanian artists Saulė, and library catalogues know at least 33 James Campbells.

Figure 3.1: All our researchers are identified with an ORCID identifier

Do not have an ORCID yet? You can register on orcid.org, it takes only a minute.

- All our artists are identified with a VIAF, ISNI, GND or similar identifier.
- All our public documents are identified with a https URL. (Now it is becoming understandable why is the file_location/on_your_sytem/events/2023_01_95_james_campell_release is so important!)

We add rich metadata. We even have a research task where we want to identify data improvement strategies!

Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe: The metadata and the dataset they describe are usually separate files. The association between

a metadata file and the dataset should be made explicit by mentioning a dataset's globally unique and persistent identifier in the metadata.

We write here about [Natas Kunas](#), but if you look for photos about this project, you find it [here](#); you can listen to it [here](#), and you may find further information about the artist named *Donatas Vaitkūnas* in libraries or rights management database. We need to connect all this information, regardless if we release scientific texts, datasets, or even event invitations. This is a technical task but requires cooperation from the creators of digital files.

Digital assets are registered or indexed in a searchable resource: we insert all our knowledge output, sound recordings, photographs, into global collections and libraries. We put visualizations on FigShare, manuscripts on Zenodo, artist information on Wikidata and Wikipedia; details of our digital assets to global library systems via OpenAIRE and Europeana, etc.

If you placed correctly named, formatted files into the right place, we will take it from here. You will be surprised how many more people will hear about your work.

3.6 FAIR Requirements (Technical)

- F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2. Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe
- F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

4 A - Accessible

The first step in (re)using data, text, sound recordings, films, photographs is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers.

4.1 OPA

Share raw (or analytic) data and materials in a way that the analysis is reproducible with minimal effort. Analytic and raw data are made available through a trusted repository. We chose GitHub as a temporary repository where all our changes can be traced; and periodically we place these materials on Zenodo, where they are stored independently from our Consortium for a very long period. Detailed instructions are provided for accessing raw data that is proprietary or contains sensitive information.

4.2 Open Science (Non-technical)

Digital assets are retrievable using a standardised communications protocol: Most data producers will use http(s) or ftp; we only use https.

The 'A' in FAIR does not necessarily mean 'open' or 'free'. Rather, it implies that one should provide the exact conditions under which the data are accessible. Hence, even heavily protected and private data can be FAIR.

Digital assets and datasets tend to degrade or disappear over time because there is a cost to maintaining an online presence for data resources. When this happens, links become invalid and users waste time hunting for data that might no longer be there. Storing the metadata generally is much easier and cheaper. Hence, principle A2 states that metadata should persist even when the data are no longer sustained.

4.3 FAIR (Technical)

A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol

A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable

- We use Zenodo and Github, because they work with https.
- A counter-examples would be Skype, Dropbox or Google Drive, which is not universally-implementable because it is proprietary
- Microsoft Exchange Server protocol is also proprietary

A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary

A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

5 I - Interoperability

The digital assets usually need to be integrated with other digital assets. In addition, the data needs to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.

- When you write a scientific article, you want to link references to other work; an informed reader or reviewer needs to know where to read more about what you summarize.
- When you release a new song or album, you need to provide DSPs, a photograph of the artist and some biographical and release information (text context).
- To calculate GDP/capita, you need to be able to successfully link GDP and population count data for the correct year, country or region.
- When we create a survey program with a multi-language question bank, we need to make sure that "Concert" is correctly matched with "Konzert" and "Koncert".

Interoperability is hard across computers, across teams, organizations, countries. Some people use Windows systems, other Mac; some use Bulgarian (Cyrillic) characters, others

Slovak or German. **Interoperability is the key to a successful team work, and a successful R&D consortium**

5.1 Tidy data

Our reproducible research practice follows the tidy data principle, which has very complex computer science and information management consequences. Still, for the lay user of data, it boils down to simplicity.

Tidy data is a standard way of mapping the meaning of a dataset to its structure. A dataset is messy or tidy depending on how rows, columns and tables are matched up with observations, variables and types. In tidy data:

- Every column is a variable. We do not use colours (our machine-to-machine pipelines is colourblind). If we need comments or specifications, we add a new column.
- Every row is an observation. Every variable belonging to Bulgaria is in the Bulgaria row, and there is one and only Bulgaria row.
- Every cell is a single value. We never merge cells! A tidy dataset has no divided columns and no divided rows.

This is often far more easier to write than to do, but still, if you can make it that simple, then you already mastered Codd's 3rd normal form framed in statistical language :)¹.

Tidy datasets are very easy to import into Excel, Google Spreadsheets, SPSS, STATA or even relational databases. Untidy texts will place you into the perpetual Data Sysiphus: every time you need the data, you need to rearrange the rows, colors, and columns, and in the meantime, you make countless errors that your senior (quality) supervisor cannot even easily detect.

Tidy data is simple data.

Most of you will not need to bother with translation to HTML or W3C compliant datacubes, or SDMX metadata codebooks, or DDI survey codebooks: this is the task of UTU and Reprex. But you must be able to provide us with inputs in this format. This requires simplicity.

5.2 Tidy text

We come from different working environments: some work only in Microsoft Word. Others only in programming consoles. Some use Apple's MacOS (or other BSD operational systems), others Linux or Unix distributions, and others use Windows in various versions and language editions.

The world wide web made it possible for us to interlink via the http(s) protocol and the HTML text markup system documents that are in any part of the world. The findability,

¹ A bit more specifically: [Tidy data](#) (informal) - [Tidy data](#) - formal. .

access and interoperability conditions of our project (FAIR and OPA) require us to create documents that adhere to the W3C standard of the world wide web texts or similar standards applied to publications, books, datasets, and visualisations.

Working with tidy texts will not separate you from your favourite word processor. You can still use Grammarly in Google Docs. You only have to make sure that your text remains simple: you refrain from adding formatting to the document if they do not adhere to a common standard that connects Windows, Mac, Unix, Word, VIM, and Posit.

- Simple text has clearly defined headings: title, subtitle, heading level 1, heading level 2, heading level 3.
- Simple text has standardised bibliographic references and footnotes.
- Simple text has standard section breaks and page breaks.
- Simple text allows the automatic insertion of tidy data (as defined earlier) or interoperable graphics (preferably PNG or for web use webp).
- Simple text uses only bold, italics, underline, and perhaps strikethrough highlighting.
- Simple text has no table of contents because the table of contents is automatically generated from headings.
- Simple text has no bibliography because it is automatically generated from standardized bibliographic entries.
- Simple text does not use footers, headers, watermarks, color boxes, because these things need to be added differently on Word, PDF, or HTML.

The markdown notation is a simple notation that allows a smooth translation to HTML, Word, DOC, EPUB, or any standard format. We can create beautiful, engaging, easy-to-find, accessible and interoperable documents if we get simple inputs from you.

See [Tidy text](#) for more information.

5.3 WP2 & Listen Local

5.4 WP3 & Survey harmonization

5.5 Bibliography

- We use the open source, free [Zotero](#) research assistant. It can work with files created by Mendeley or OneNote. If you do not have a Zotero account, you should consider it after consulting our annex: [▶ Annex / Collaboration tools / Zotero](#)
- For publications, we export (and slightly modify) citation data to BibLatex, a text format that is required for most scientific journal/book Tex templates. Because no research assistant exports precisely the same way, manual adjustment is always required, so we keep up-to-date .bib collections on Github that are manually adjusted after exporting from Zotero, Mendeley, OneNote or downloaded directly from scientific libraries.

5.6 European

Humans should be able to exchange and interpret each other's data, and digital assets (so preferably do not use dead languages). But this also applies to computers, meaning that data should be readable for machines without the need for specialised or ad hoc algorithms, translators, or mappings; and this plays a crucial importance in our research, particularly :

The main goal of this principle is to provide a “common understanding” of digital objects by means of a language for knowledge representation to be used to represent these objects.

5.7 FAIR (Technical)

I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation

The RDF extensible knowledge representation model is a way to describe and structure datasets. You can refer to the Dublin Core Schema as an example.

I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

When we are describing data or metadata, we often use vocabularies that provide the terms or concepts that are adequate to represent their content.

I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data, balanced against the time/energy involved in making a good data model.

6 R - Reusability

The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.

6.1 Non-technical

- Describe the scope of your data: for what purpose was it generated/collected? Mention any particularities or limitations about the data that other users should be aware of.
- Specify the date of generation/collection of the data, the lab conditions, who prepared the data, the parameter settings, the name and version of the software used.
- Is it raw or processed data?
- Ensure that all variable names are explained or self-explanatory (i.e., defined in the research field's controlled vocabulary).
- Clearly specify and document the version of the archived and/or reused data.

6.2 FAIR (Technical)

R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

Under 'I', we covered elements of technical interoperability. R1.1 is about legal interoperability.

R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

7 Open Collaboration

Open collaboration is any “system of innovation or production that relies on goal-oriented yet loosely coordinated participants who interact to create a product (or service) of economic value, which is made available to contributors and noncontributors alike.”

It is prominently observed in open source software, or the creation of TEDx and Wikipedia.

- ☒ goods of [economic value](#)
- ☒ [open access](#) to contribute and consume
- ☒ [interaction](#) and exchange
- ☒ purposeful yet [loosely coordinated](#) work

An annual conference dedicated to the research and practice of open collaboration is the International Symposium on Open Collaboration ([OpenSym](#)).

7.1 Good economic value

7.2 Open Access

7.3 Interaction and Exchange

7.3.1 Simple, non-intrusive, secure communications

When you work with dozens of organizations employing hundreds of people, the last thing you want to get is endless cc: emails and bcc: emails that clutter your mailbox day and night.

You also want to keep your private communications channels, like Whatsapp or Messgenger free from work messages.

Keybase is our preferred tool to get in touch with us and ask questions, instead of emails, Whatsapp/Viber/Messenger/Telegram/Signal, that not everybody uses, and some people use for private matters only. *Keybase* is an open-source, free, privacy- and security-concerned alternative to *Slack* and similar chat-based collaboration tools. It is fully integrated with Zoom (which owns it recently) and Google Meet, so you can switch immediately to audio or video calls. Our observatories and Listen Local have their Keybase channels where you can interact with other curators and developers. ⇨ [Annex / Collaboration tools / Keybase](#) ☒ [keybase.io](#)

7.3.2 Respectful, inclusive work environment

You must abide the ☒ [Contributor Covenant Code of Conduct](#) (but *need not send* us proof) of pledging to make participation in our community a harassment-free experience for everyone, regardless of age, body size, visible or invisible disability, ethnicity, sex characteristics, gender identity and expression, level of experience, education, socio-economic status, nationality, personal appearance, race, caste, color, religion, or sexual identity and orientation. (See [translations](#) and the related [FAQ](#).)

Contributor Covenant

[Home](#) [Adopters](#) [Latest Version](#) [Translations](#) [FAQ](#)

CONTRIBUTOR COVENANT CODE OF CONDUCT

Our Pledge

We as members, contributors, and leaders pledge to make participation in our community a harassment-free experience for everyone, regardless of age, body size, visible or invisible disability, ethnicity, sex characteristics, gender identity and expression, level of experience, education, socio-economic status, nationality, personal appearance, race, caste, color, religion, or sexual identity and orientation.

We pledge to act and interact in ways that contribute to an open, welcoming, diverse, inclusive, and healthy community.

7.4 Purposeful yet loosely coordinated work

7.4.1 Single file system that is secure and managed (overwrite) group conflicts

We use GitHub, because it meets EU FAIR and OPA requirements, and works in a far more interoperable (and affordable) way than *Microsoft Sharepoint*, or *Microsoft OneDrive*, and *Google Drive*, or *Drobox* for sharing file resources.

7.4.2 One problem, one issue, one solution

7.4.3 Simple task, milestone and deadline management

Github, a Git-based open source and free service (currently owned by Microsoft) is our tool for a very simple task tracking in a kanban-style. We use it in the [Digital Music Observatory](#), in the [Open Collections Network](#) (used in Listen Local, WP2 Open Music Europe), because it complies with FAIR and OPA requirements (see earlier: [Findable](#), [Accessible](#), [I](#), [Reusable](#) work), and it is free to use for most users.

Image credit:

[Anyway Kanban](#)

For tracking tasks, you only need a web browser and an account on Github. All project managers in our data observatories must have one, and curators are highly encouraged to join them, too. There are thousands of alternatives for *Github's kanban*, but we use it, because it integrates well with a far better product than i.e., *Microsoft Sharepoint*, or *Microsoft OneDrive*, and *Google Drive*, or *Drobox* for sharing file resources, such a clear and processed documents, spreadsheets, SPSS files, website elements, media files.

Because Github is a more advanced tool *for sharing files* than the aforementioned shared drives (it prevents the creation of conflicting versions of the same text, table or photograph), and because it integrates with a simple task management, it is also far more complicated to set-up/install and learn. Github is a very simple for task management, to synchronize the file assets behind the tasks requires a bit of attention. But if you decide to go this way, you can build websites with us, blogs, publish journal articles, or even books. In scientific or open-source software cooperation using Github is fairly standard, so it will improve your ability to interact with colleagues. A curator does not need to use Github, unless he or she wants to cooperate on scientific outputs. github.com

- If you have an existing Github account, please give us your [Github account ID](#) as the preferred way of exchanging files.
- If you do not have one, please create a free account with a username that you would use professionally.
- Please consider synching your files via Github with us after consulting our annex: [Annex / Collaboration tools / Github](#).
- We can automate the issuing of DOI's to all your figures, code, text automatically via Zenodo and Github.

Check out our repositories on GitHub: - Repository: Report on the European Music Economy (Open Music Europe 2023d) - Repository: Report on Music Diversity and Circulation in Europe (Open Music Europe 2023a) - Repository: Report on Music, Society, and Citizenship in Europe (Open Music Europe 2023c) - Report on Music Innovation &

7.5 Bibliography management

- We use the open source, free [Zotero](#) research assistant. It can work with files created by Mendeley or OneNote. If you do not have a Zotero account, you should consider it after consulting our annex: [Annex / Collaboration tools / Zotero](#)
- For publications, we export (and slightly modify) citation data to BibLatex, a text format that is required for most scientific journal/book Tex templates. Because no research assistant exports precisely the same way, manual adjustment is always required, so we keep up-to-date .bib collections on Github that are manually adjusted after exporting from Zotero, Mendeley, OneNote or downloaded directly from scientific libraries.

8 Tidy Data

Our reproducible research practice follows the tidy data principle, which has very complex computer science and information management consequences. Still, for the lay user of data, it boils down to simplicity.

Tidy data is a standard way of mapping the meaning of a dataset to its structure. A dataset is messy or tidy depending on how rows, columns and tables are matched up with observations, variables and types.

Figure 8.1: Following three rules makes a dataset tidy: variables are in columns, observations are in rows, and values are in cells. From *R For Data Science - 12. Tidy Data*

In tidy data: - Every column is a variable. We do not use colours (our machine-to-machine pipelines is colourblind). If we need comments or specifications, we add a new column. - Every row is an observation. Every variable belonging to Bulgaria is in the Bulgaria row, and there is one and only Bulgaria row. - Every cell is a single value. We never merge cells! A tidy dataset has no divided columns and no divided rows.

This is often far more easier to write than to do, but still, if you can make it that simple, then you already mastered Codd's 3rd normal form framed in statistical language.

Tidy data is data in Codd's 3rd normal form, but with the constraints framed in statistical language, and the focus put on a single dataset rather than the many connected datasets common in relational databases.

Figure 8.2: Tidy data always has two forms: wide and long. From *R For Data Science - 12. Tidy Data*.

Our task in WP4 is to help tidying some datasets that are commonly used in music, and surveying, and which will be used in WP1 (linking royalty accounts with SDMX compatible statistical data), WP2 (linking various, special purpose music data resources), and WP3 (DDI survey datasets, DDI survey codebooks). See more: [dataset: Create Data Frames that are Easier to Exchange and Reuse](#).

9 Tidy Text

We create interconnected, interoperable (web) resources: we want to ensure that our research results are findable, accessible, and reusable. The world wide web has been a source of high interoperability and findability in the last 30 years with the introduction of the http protocol and the standardization of the HTML text markup language.

```
- icon: fa-eu-emblem
  icon_pack: far
  name: Consortium on CORDIS
  url: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101095295

# Featured image
image:
  caption: "[Dominika Semanáková](https://music.dataobservatory.eu/authors/dominika_senanakova/)"
  focal_point: "center"
  placement: 2
  preview_only: true

tags:
- Open Music Europe
- Slovakia
- Smart Policy Document
---
```

The 'Open Music Europe Consortium', Reprex and SOZA signed a Memorandum of Understanding with the Ministry of Culture of t University of Bratislava, SOZA on utilizing the Open Policy Analysis results.

<td style="text-align: center;">{{< figure src="img/blogposts_2023/MoU_signature_20230306_02_2x1.jpg" caption="From left t Board (SOZA); [Dr James Edwards](https://music.dataobservatory.eu/authors/james_edwards/) Open Music Europe program direct Rado Kutas, state secretary; Tomáš Mikš, SOZA; [Daniel Antal](https://reprex.nl/author/daniel-antal/), co-founder of Repre (https://music.dataobservatory.eu/authors/dominika_senanakova/), " numbered="false" >}}</td>

This cooperation is a very important milestone for our the Digital Music Observatory: our reproducible research will be us context in an EU member state. Our [Slovak Music Industry Report](https://music.dataobservatory.eu/publication/slovak_music_practice_within_the_slovak_republic).

We will create Live Policy Document on Music Economy, on Diversity and Circulation, on Music and Society, and on Music Inn We will contribute with automatically refreshed web resources and high-quality indicators about cultural and creative indu will be used to monitor the implementation of the 'Cultural and Creative Industries Strategy of the Slovak Republic 2030' priemyslu Slovenskej republiky 2030)(https://www.culture.gov.sk/ministerstvo/strategia-kultury-a-kreativneho-priemyslu-2030

Figure 9.1: Our entire website is created from simple markdown text. See Chapter 13.

All our output needs to be converted to HTML, but that does not mean that we need to work in an HTML editor. However, the need of interoperability among operating systems (Windows, MacOS, Linux) and software packages (at least from Word, Libre, Google Docs to HTML, preferably to PDF, too) requires a simple, common notation.

Markdown is a much simplified HTML text notation intended to work well with word processors.

Or, if you want Word output, then instead of HTML, Word is rendered. Or PDF. Or EPUB.

9.1 Try it out

There are countless Markdown editors. Because Markdown is so simple, you can, if you want to, edit markdown files in Notepad, WordPad (Windows) or VIM (Linux).

Most word processors support markdown. For example, Google Docs has a [free extension](#) that converts and document from Docs to markdown.

There are several online Markdown editors that you can use to try writing in Markdown. [Dillinger](#) is one of the best online Markdown editors. Just open the site and start typing in the left pane. A preview of the rendered document appears in the right pane.

9.1.1 Communicate using Markdown

This is a course for new GitHub users. You need to log into your (free) GitHub account to use it.

- **Who is this for:** New developers, new GitHub users, and students.
 - **What you'll learn:** Use Markdown to add lists, images, and links in a comment or text file.
 - **What you'll build:** We'll update a plain text file and add Markdown formatting, and you can use this file to start your own GitHub Pages site.
 - **Prerequisites:** In this course you will work with pull requests as well as edit files. If these things aren't familiar to you, we recommend you take the [Introduction to GitHub](#) course, first!
 - **How long:** This course is five steps long and takes less than one hour to complete.
1. Right-click **Start course** and open the [link](#) in a new tab.

 Start course

2. In the new tab, follow the prompts to create a new repository.
 - For owner, choose your personal account or an organization to host the repository.
 - We recommend creating a public repository—private repositories will [use Actions minutes](#).

Create a new repository from course-name

The new repository will start with the same files and folders as [skills/course-name](#).

Owner * Repository name *

/

Great repository names are short and memorable. Need inspiration? How about [friendly-chainsaw?](#)

Description (optional)

Public
Anyone on the internet can see this repository. You choose who can commit.

Private
You choose who can see and commit to this repository.

Include all branches
Copy all branches from `skills/introduction-to-github` and not just `main`.

ⓘ You are creating a public repository in your personal account.

[Create repository from template](#)

3. After your new repository is created, wait about 20 seconds, then refresh the page. Follow the step-by-step instructions in the new repository's README.

9.1.2 Make it look good

You can simplify a Word document, for example, via uploading to Google Docs and sending it through the [free extension](#) to get a markdown document. But usually you would like to work the other way around! It is a better practice to write a text in markdown, and when ready, add it to a nice PDF, Word, or website (blog) HTML template. This way you keep your text (and citations) simple and interoperable, and you can reuse the same text many times over.

9.2 Markdown syntax

- [Basic Syntax](#)
- [Extended Syntax](#)

9.3 Use your favorite application

Working with tidy texts will not separate you from your favourite word processor. You can still use Grammarly in Google Docs. You only have to make sure that your text remains simple: you refrain from adding formatting to the document if they do not adhere to a common standard that connects Windows, Mac, Unix, Word, VIM, and Posit.

- Simple text has clearly defined headings: title, subtitle, heading level 1, heading level 2, heading level 3.

- ☒ Simple text has standardised bibliographic references and footnotes.
- ☒ Simple text has standard section breaks and page breaks.
- ☒ Simple text allows the automatic insertion of tidy data (as defined earlier) or interoperable graphics (preferably PNG or for web use webp).
- ☒ Simple text uses only bold, italics, underline, and perhaps strikethrough highlighting.
- ☐ Simple text has no table of contents because the table of contents is automatically generated from headings.
- ☐ Simple text has no bibliography because it is automatically generated from standardized bibliographic entries.
- ☐ Simple text does not use footers, headers, watermarks, color boxes, because these things need to be added differently on Word, PDF, or HTML.

10 Standard File Structure

Standardize the file structure so that materials are organized in a way that is accessible to an informed reader.

OPA Level 3: All project components are organized in a selfcontained folder using a Standard File Structure (SFS), and a readme file is included.

We use a standardized file system that is standard in the R open statistical environment. While it is an R standard, it is not unusual for researchers using Python or another programming language for their work.

Figure 10.1: All project components are organized in a selfcontained folder using a Standard File Structure (SFS), and a readme file is included.

10.1 Ignored files in .gitignore

We place a list of folders and files that are ignored for synchronization from the user's client computer to Github and beyond. These are usually passwords, login credentials, project management or log files used by your IDE or other work environment. We by default, excluded all Posit/RStudio standards, and usually all Jupiter Notebook standards, and a few Windows/Mac specific files. We also ignore a standard folder called `not_included`, which serves as the place of your personal scrapbook, sandbox, that you do not want to share with anybody.

10.2 Data folders

We have two data folders, which may have numerous subfolders.

`data-raw`: Raw, unprocessed data, as received, downloaded, collected. Please try to ingest data as well-documented as possible. If the ingestion is not done by our reproducible tools that log the download, copying, and bibliographic references, you are requested to create a standard bibliographic reference for any data that you place here. You can use your favorite citation management tool or join our shared, open-source, Zotero account, but eventually, the data asset must be added to the `bib/data-raw.bib` files as a standard, BibLatex data citation. We use the DataCite standard, which almost fully corresponds to DublinCore.

`data`: This folder contains the processed data or our outputs. Any data here must adhere to the tidy data principle and be documented by DataCite standards. We are developing a tool, `dataset`, which will do this automatically in WP4. We can investigate a Python connector for this if there is a need for that. Bibliographic reference folders.

10.3 Referencing and attribution

`bib`: Contains all bibliography: used citations, data used, visualisation used, datasets created, visualizations created, public text document outputs created.

10.4 Visualisation folders

We save visualisations in folders corresponding to the file format. This is the best way to ensure that pandoc or any compiles has the necessary plugins to work with the visualizations. Every visualization that is intended to made pubic gets a bibliographic citation and a globally unique DOI identifier.

`png`: contains visualisations in Portable Network Graphics format (our preferred format.)

`jpg`: Contains visualization in Joint Photographic Experts Group format.

`webp`: Contains visualisations in WebP is an open image file format developed by Google intended as a replacement for JPEG, PNG, and GIF file formats. We prefer this for content intended for web use (presentations, blogposts), because it works much faster and better with browsers than PNG or JPG.

[...] You can use other formats if necessary.

10.5 Program code folders

R: contains any script in the R language.

Py: contains script in the Python language [if there is any, create the folder at first time use].

CPP: contains script in the C++ language [if there is any, create the folder at first time use].

10.6 Text markup folders

tex: Tex document markup language templates. css : CSS style templates [if there is any, create the folder at first time use].

10.7 Final text outputs

The final text outputs are in the `_book` folder. They are weaved together by pandoc, knitr and bookdown if they are made of several source files, hence the name book. If they are created from a single file, they are not technically a book but they are here in HTML, EPUB, PDF, or docx or pptx formats.

10.8 Source texts

The source texts are stored in Rmd, md, or tex files in the main folder. We prefer Rmd, because Posit can integrate well R, Python, C++ code, and via pandoc and knitr various Latex and Word compilers. But you can use any flavor of .md or .tex.

Rmd is technically a plain .md with a special YAML heading for machine use and optional R, Python, or C++ code placeholders. If you decide to use other .md editors, we will create an empty template that contains the non-visible YAML heading for machine processing.

11 Collaboration tools

11.1 Keybase

No more long emails. Nobody's left out. No more misunderstandings. No more waiting for feedback.

What do we need?

- A simple-to-use communication tool where you can opt-in to be informed on a real time basis, or completely ignore us for days – similar to Whatsapp Group, Microsoft Teams, Google Hangout, Slack;
- A single, secure storage for shared documents – similar to Google Drive, Microsoft One Drive, Dropbox;
- An integration with Github – a critical feature to at least the part of our team that is working on software code or long-form technical documentations;

- Ability to oversee communications with more than 50 people with an option to streamline per topic, group, etc.;
- To avoid using emails boxes, Whatsapp, Viber, etc. – part-timers are not flooded with messages at all times, while full-timers can reach out to each other at any time;
- A space where we can communicate all the time without interrupting calls and meetings with clients on other platforms; An integration to a project management tool that we will use for larger projects;
- A tool as simple as possible, light touch;
- Since we work in the open source, open data, open collaboration community, we would like to use something that is open source – but we are willing to pay for solutions.

And the winner is....KEYBASE.IO

Keybase is a very neat, simple, lightweight team management / chat / social networking application that is extremely focused on privacy, security and encryption.

Keybase Key features

- Secure instant messaging, even with a timed self-destruction feature (e.g. for sharing passwords); Starts a Google Meet or Zoom video call natively with a single command;
- Brings your Whatsapp chat to the more private and secure keybase chat on the fly;
- Team chat rooms in real time. You can filter where you want to be involved, and you can always opt-out;

-K-Drive (similar to OneDrive, Google Drive, Dropbox) – only for our team, and fully encrypted; Works with Github, and it even offers a more private version of Private Github Repos, encrypted gits; An integration with other platforms; It is neat, open source, simple, clean, and usually appreciated more in the open source community than Slack, its big corporation rival.

Practical steps you need to follow to use Keybase

1. Download & install Keybase from <https://keybase.io/> on your computer. An easy procedure. Create yourself a professional login name – similarly to a professional github account, a professional email, etc. (you cannot change the name afterwards)
2. Once you log in to the computer, go to *Devices*, and *Create a paper key*. Write this on paper, or print it, and store it somewhere very safe (not near your computer). This to recover the access in case you lose access to all your devices.

3. You can use Keybase simultaneously on multiple devices – Install Keybase on your smartphone, tablet or any other device. You will be guided through installation & paired with your computer.
4. Shall you need them, you have *two recovery options*: the paper key and your smartphone.
5. If your smartphone breaks down and needs a replacement, you can add from your computer your new phone and deactivate the old one.
6. Once you are in, look up antaldaniel.
7. After a handshake Daniel will assist your smooth transition, help you find ways to our shared files, your project's files, and set up filters, so you are not flooded with information, while never left out, unless you choose to.
8. Initially, we set up the following “Big teams”, as Keybase calls them, and we will send an invitation to join:
 - `reprexfriends` for prospective team members, friends, and hoped-for-cooperation partners – partly for people we are discreetly asking to join us, or who want to know more about some of our work and cooperate with us;
 - `reprexcommunity` is an open landing page for anybody, it is a public interface. If you every land there antaldaniel will take you to the appropriate, otherwise invisible team room.

Each big team has four special members for a smooth transition: Daniel and Zuzana to assist you with getting familiar with Keybase, zoombot (just type `!zoom` to create a Zoom call with the team members present) and meetbot (that does the same with Google Meet, `!meet`). Daniel will gradually withdraw from some of the teams, once their support is not needed, though each team will have at least one Reprex co-founder present. We invite everybody to at least one team, but you can sign up to as many as you like, shall you find that convenient.

9. Whenever you are in a situation you want to ignore us (e.g. because you sit in your dayjob), just do it. If you have a smartphone, we are there, separated from your Whatsapp friends, work emails, and you can always check on us. We can always send you a secure (and even encrypted) message to get in touch, if needed. However, we will never ever bother you with long emails, Whatsapp messages and other annoying things.

Let's keep things short, give access to the full picture when needed, and let you find out what mix of response time, details and filters works best for you.

11.2 Github

Git in general, and **Github** in particular is a simultaneous collaboration form for any distributed team work - writing, programming, design work. Git is an open source software which makes sure that your teamwork files are always synchronized, clashes are avoided

(you modify the same part of a file at the same time with Daniel.) The only hard part to move to Git is to make sure that Git properly works on your computer - it needs to be installed differently on all Linux distros, Mac OSX version all Windows versions. On Windows, you must make sure that Git is on the startup path. Once you are there, you'll life will be much easier.

Github is the most popular open collaboration platform for open source software editors. If you do not write code, you will not contribute to our source files, but with a Github id you ask questions, take on tasks and report them ready on our project dashboard.

11.2.1 Introduction to GitHub

This is a course is suitable for new GitHub users. You need to log into your (free) GitHub account to use it.

- **Who is this for:** New developers, new GitHub users, and students.
- **What you'll learn:** We'll introduce repositories, branches, commits, and pull requests.
- **What you'll build:** We'll make a short Markdown file you can use as your [profile README](#).
- **Prerequisites:** None. This course is a great introduction for your first day on GitHub.
- **How long:** This course is four steps long and takes less than one hour to complete.

Course tips:

- Glossary terms will be *emphasised* and linked to their definition.
- This [course](#) includes optional video links. Look for the :tv: emoji and follow the link to the video.

11.2.2 Review Pull Requests

This is a course is suitable for new GitHub users. You need to log into your (free) GitHub account to use it.

All great projects start with collaboration. Pull requests are the foundation of teamwork on GitHub — and pull request reviews give you the ability to work together and discuss changes specific to a pull request by commenting, requesting changes, or approving.

- **Who is this for:** Developers, new GitHub users, users new to Git, students, managers, teams.
- **What you'll learn:** When and how to request a review; how to provide a review of someone else's pull request.
- **What you'll build:** We'll be reviewing a pull request for a simple game.

- **Prerequisites:** We assume you are familiar with creating branches, commits, and pull requests—you can learn this in our [Introduction to GitHub](#) course.
- **How long:** This course is five steps long and takes less than 30 minutes to complete.

11.3 How to start this course

1. Right-click **Start course** and open the [link](#) in a new tab.

2. In the new tab, follow the prompts to create a new repository.
 - For owner, choose your personal account or an organization to host the repository.
 - We recommend creating a public repository—private repositories will [use Actions minutes](#).

Create a new repository from course-name

The new repository will start with the same files and folders as [skills/course-name](#).

Owner * Repository name *

 username / course-name ✓

Great repository names are short and memorable. Need inspiration? How about [friendly-chainsaw](#)?

Description (optional)

 Public
Anyone on the internet can see this repository. You choose who can commit.

 Private
You choose who can see and commit to this repository.

Include all branches
Copy all branches from [skills/introduction-to-github](#) and not just main.

 You are creating a public repository in your personal account.

[Create repository from template](#)

3. After your new repository is created, wait about 20 seconds, then refresh the page. Follow the step-by-step instructions in the new repository's README.

11.3.1 Resolve editing conflicts on GitHub

Merge conflicts happen when two people make changes to the same file on GitHub—a common occurrence when you're working with others. While resolving differences might involve some discussion, merge conflicts don't have to be scary. This course guides you through the steps to finding the best merge conflict solution, so your team can keep building.

- **Who is this for:** New developers, new GitHub users, users new to Git, students, managers, teams.
- **What you'll learn:** What merge conflicts are, how you resolve merge conflicts, how to reduce merge conflicts.
- **What you'll build:** We'll work with a short Markdown resume file in this course.
- **Prerequisites:** We recommend taking [Introduction to GitHub](#) prior to this course.
- **How long:** This course is three steps long and takes less than 30 minutes to complete.

11.4 How to start this course

1. Right-click **Start course** and open the [link](#) in a new tab.

 Start course

2. In the new tab, follow the prompts to create a new repository.
 - For owner, choose your personal account or an organization to host the repository.
 - We recommend creating a public repository—private repositories will [use Actions minutes](#).
3. After your new repository is created, wait about 20 seconds, then refresh the page. Follow the step-by-step instructions in the new repository's README.

11.5 Zotero

We have shared bibliographies on the open source, free [Zotero](#) research assistant and we have a closed bibliography repository with BibLatex files on Github for the material that refer to in open science, open policy analysis, data science, and each other's work. The best place to share readings, bibliographies is *Zotero*, for preparing publications the Github account.

Here is a [short tutorial](#) on how to synchronize your personal bibliographic reference collection with the Digital Music Observatory group library.

- Set up a free [Zotero.org](#) user account if you do not have it already.
- Open Zotero preferences (via the ⚙️ gear menu) and select the **Sync** tab.
- Enter your Zotero user name and password.
- Check the “sync automatically” box.
- Check both boxes under File Syncing and choose Zotero storage for My Library. This will sync your PDF attachments as well as citations (more info).
- Click the green circular arrow button at the top right corner of the Zotero window. Zotero will upload your library to the server.
- If you look at the screenshot below, you see *My Library*, this is your original private library. This is not synchronised to the Digital Music Observatory (or other) group.
- You will see as separate collections the libraries of groups that you are member of. You can drag and drop references between your own personal library and the group libraries.

12 Personal and Research Tools

12.1 Write in Markdown

We create web resources: we want to ensure that our research results are findable, accessible, and reusable. The world wide web has been a source of high interoperability and findability in the last 30 years with the introduction of the http protocol and the standardization of the HTML text markup language.

All our output needs to be converted to HTML, but that does not mean that we need to work in an HTML editor. However, the need of interoperability among operating systems (Windows, MacOs, Linux) and software packages (at least from Word, Libre, Google Docs to HTML, preferably to PDF, too) requires a simple, common notation.

Markdown is a much simplified HTML text notation intended to work well with word processors.

Or, if you want Word output, then instead of HTML, Word is rendered. Or PDF. Or EPUB.

12.2 Try it out

There are countless Markdown editors. Because Markdown is so simple, you can, if you want to, edit markdown files in Notepad, WordPad (Windows) or VIM (Linux).

Most word processors support markdown. For example, Google Docs has a [free extension](#) that converts and document from Docs to markdown.

There are several online Markdown editors that you can use to try writing in Markdown. [Dillinger](#) is one of the best online Markdown editors. Just open the site and start typing in the left pane. A preview of the rendered document appears in the right pane.

12.3 Make it look good

You can simplify a Word document, for example, via uploading to Google Docs and sending it through the [free extension](#) to get a markdown document. But usually you would like to work the other way around! It is a better practice to write a text in markdown, and when ready, add it to a nice PDF, Word, or website (blog) HTML template. This way you keep your text (and citations) simple and interoperable, and you can reuse the same text many times over.

12.4 Markdown syntax

- [Basic Syntax](#)
- [Extended Syntax](#)

12.5 Biblatex programmable bibliographies and citations

The biblatex format is the most likely format that you will use for scientific publications. You can export a collection, or more practically, a folder in a collection as a starting point, into the BibLatex format from Zotero (introduced in the previous chapter [Collaboration Tools - Zotero](#). See [Zotero](#) as a graphic UI, like Windows 11 or MacOS as a human-readable reference database, and the biblatex is a machine-readable (DOS or BSD) part. The standard output from [Zotero](#) is a good start, but usually, it is not perfect. Please open the `bib/example.bib` file and see an example of how to make a reference more usable and interoperable.

@book{example_id_2015,—you will use this in your text author = {Doe, Jane}, editor = {Doe, Joe}, date = {2015-06-06}, year = {2015},—some programs do not convert from date automatically month = {06},—not needed with books, journals day = {06},—not needed with books, journals doi = {<a Digital Object identifier code goes here>},—connects to web resources isbn = {<an International Standard Book Number identifier goes here>}, urldate = {2023-07-12}, title = {This is an {EXAMPLE} title}, — the EXAMPLE remains UPPERCASE abstract = {This is the {Place} for an {AbStrAcT}.},—Keep it short, or omit it url = {http://example.com/title}, issn = {<an International Standard Serial Number here>},—connects with library catalogues publisher = {{Digital Music Observatory}}, keywords = {Example},—use only standardized keywords, like [LCSH](#) }

A .bib file is a text file that you can edit in Notepad or WordPad on Windows, VIM on Linux, in RStudio, or any text editor (not word processor like Word.) It contains the notation of *programmable bibliographic* references.

The first thing you see in bib/example.bib that it is a book (@book). Other usual formatting options are @misc for any document, @article for a journal article, website for a website, etc. If your document has an ISBN, it should always be reported as a book because the easiest matching of the bibliographic entry with the actual source is via International Standard Book Number (ISBN).

Download the example bib from our repository: <https://github.com/dataobservatory-eu/contributors/blob/main/bib/opa.bib>—press the ‘Raw’ button to exit the web preview and get the file as it is.

Spaces, like in most programming languages, are not processed. urldate = {2023-07-12} and urldate= {2023-07-12} and urldate={2023-07-12} are identical in meaning. Use a consistent editing for readability.

12.5.1 Basic biblatex formatting

In biblatex, each field has a value. For example, year=2015 stands for the publication year 2015. When text is used and not a number, for example, month={March}, you use the {} sign as a quotation. The most likely formatting error is with {}.

- **Simple values** have their own standard readings: author={Doe, Jane} will translate to J. Doe or Jane Doe. The author={Jane Doe} will translate to D. Jane, or Doe Jane, because the standard name setting is GivenName, FamilyName.
- **Double quotation** can override whatever standards. For example, author={{Jane Doe}} will always read as Jane Doe and not Doe Jane or J. Doe. This is what you use with institutional authors. When no person is named as an author, for example, in the case of a statute law text, use the double quotation. author={{European Commission}} will read European Commission, but author={European Commission} will read C. European.
- **Add a language identifier**, for example, for English language books: language = {en}. Your title will be converted to the linguistic requirements of the given

language. If you use multiple languages, and you want to avoid English title case for a Slovak or Hungarian document, then double quote the `title={{This is a sentence case title}}` will be `This is a sentence case title`, but `title = {{This is sentence case}}` will be overwritten to `This is Sentence Case` if your default language is English.

- If you use an **acronym**, then you always have to use double quotation. The role of the EU in global politics must be written `title = {The role of the {EU} in global politics}`; otherwise, the EU part will be converted to `Eu` in English and `eu` in Slovak. In this case, every word will be captions as required by your main document, but the EU part will always remain EU.

12.5.2 Minimum citation standards

- We usually use **Author-Year citation formats**, so the `author={}` and `year={}` format should be always filled in. Zotero exports the publication date as `date={2015-06-06}`, which, depending on what program you use, may be translated to `year={2015}` or not. For full interoperability it is recommended to make sure by hand editing to have both. Because 2015 is a number, you can either write `year=2015` or `year={2015}`.
- **Multiple authors** are separated by `and` or `AND`. Jane and Joe Doe should be written `author={Jane, Doe AND Joe, Doe}` or `author = {Jane, Doe AND {Joe Doe}}`. For complex names, like Spanish names, it may be confusing when the next name starts, so using `AND` in uppercase makes your citations easier to review. Beware, `author = {Jane Doe, Joe Doe}` will resolve to `J. D. Joe Doe`. The `,` separates the `GivenName` from the `FamilyName`, and not the two authors. Multiple authors must be separated by the `AND` command.
- Record when you **updated** the records. The `urldate={2023-07-07}` specifies when you last checked the bibliography (if the item exists, can be found.) It is not a mandatory field for books, journal articles, but it is for ephemeral documents, websites. For your own consistency, please, always fill it in. If we have a very old URL date, usually it is a good practice to check if the document is still there.
- Use and an **object identifier**: To use inline in a text document, for example, to quote the dummy example quotation, in markdown we write `[@example_id_2015]` and then the `example_id_2015` citation will be present in the correct formatting in your reference list.

The `example_id_2015` is the ID of your reference. It is a good practice to use only lower case, `_`, or `-` and numbers, because it works with programming languages, too. Using an empty space, like `example id` is a bad practice, and likely will not work. Try to create IDs that are easy to remember. For example, if you cite many laws, try to give each legal text a similar ID.

A minimal, programmable bibliographic reference is

```
@book{example_id_2015, author = {Doe, Jane}, editor = {Doe, Joe}, date = {2015-06-06}, year = {2015}, urldate = {2023-07-12}, title = {This is an {EXAMPLE} title}}`
```

The **most common mistakes** are these:

- A field= is missing
- The start { or the end } of a quotation is missing, especially if there is a double quotation that is not finished like title="{The role of the {EU} instead of title="{The role of the {EU}"}
- The fields are not separated by a single , coma. You can use any number of spaces and tabs for formatting (tabs will be translated into spaces in a text editor), but you always must divide fields with a , sign. > author = {Jane Doe}, editor = year = 2015,

is a problem because you forgot to fill out the field, an empty field should be

```
author = {Jane Doe}, editor = {}, year = 2015,
```

or it should just be omitted. If there is no editor information, either leave an empty text field {} or leave out the editor-{ . . . }, part altogether.

```
author = {Jane Doe},, year = 2015,
```

is a problem because the program is expecting a field between the two , , signs. This happens if you delete an empty field, but accidentally leave the comma there.

12.5.3 Linked Open Data, PIDs

The best connection of our documents and bibliographies with global libraries is persistent identifiers or PIDs. If you use a PID, we can find the reference in global libraries, databases, or correct records; see new editions. You should always fill out the following PID fields.

- doi = {10.5281/zenodo.8096811}: a document identifier. Books, journals usually have DOIs, but also manuscripts, individual charts, tables, datasets. This DOI will resolve to a *deferenced* URL, i.e. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096811>. Dereferencing means that it immediately redirects you to the place where the document is actually available. Try the link out!
- isbn = {1501122185}: Only books have it, so the document must be a @book type. A book may have several ISBNs, because the paper and e-book version has different ISBN; and the translations and editions, too. Citing the correct ISBN is important for page numbering. A different format or edition may change text, and the page numbers will not add up. You should quote the ISBN that you used. If you downloaded a document with ISBN, use the electronic version on the Colophon or Impressum page. Try out for example <https://isbnsearch.org/>, i.e. <https://isbnsearch.org/isbn/1501122185>.
- issn = {1725-2423}: periodic publication have it. It often happens that a book has a DOI and an ISSN, too, in this case, please try to record all of them. Try to paste 1725-

2423 to <https://portal.issn.org/>, and you will get <https://portal.issn.org/resource/ISSN/1725-2423>.

12.5.4 Keywords

To make our documents findable, and to be able to find related citations in our bibliographies, we must use the keywords field.

12.5.5 Comprehensive BibLatex documentation

The [biblatex Package. Programmable Bibliographies and Citations](#). You find this reference in `bib/openscience.bib` as `@ctan_biblatex_2023`, which will resolve to (Philip, Moritz, and Philipp 2023, `) (check it out in the bibliography!)

```
@manual{ctan_biblatex_2023, title = {The biblatex Package. Programmable  
Bibliographies and Citations}, author = {Philip, Kime AND Moritz, Wemheuer  
AND Philipp, Lehman}, year = {2023}, month = {03}, day = {05}, date = {2023-03-  
05}, note = {TEX package version 3.19}, url =  
{https://mirror.lyrahosting.com/CTAN/macros/latex/contrib/biblatex/doc/biblat  
ex.pdf} }
```

13 Publishing

13.1 Web Publishing

Our publishing tools are standard and open source. We create websites that use standard HTML, and CSS, with some light JavaScript. We use automation to generate these (static) websites from simple assets.

- ☒ Tidy text (see 9), or markdown text, can be edited with any word processor or text editor.
- ☒ Standard PNG files (if needed, JPEG files), or, Webp files, which are much faster in browsers.
- ☒ We use standard bibliographic references (.bib) files with BibLatex. BibLatex can be edited with any editor, but it is best exported from your favorite citation management tool.
- ☒ We create presentations using only HTML, CSS, and some light Javascript (the reveal.js library.)

Naturally, you can upload any pptx, docs, epub or pdf files to our websites.

The post [Cooperation with the Slovak Ministry of Culture and Other Slovak Partners](#) is created from the simple, tidy markdown text above that you can check out in our standard file system [here](#).

```

- icon: fa-eu-euro
  icon_pack: far
  name: Consortium on CORDIS
  url: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101095295

# Featured image
image:
  caption: "[Dominika Semanáková](https://music.dataobservatory.eu/authors/dominika_semanakova/)"
  focal_point: "center"
  placement: 2
  preview_only: true

tags:
- Open Music Europe
- Slovakia
- Smart Policy Document
---
```

The 'Open Music Europe Consortium', Reprex and SOZA signed a Memorandum of Understanding with the Ministry of Culture of t University of Bratislava, SOZA on utilizing the Open Policy Analysis results.

<td style="text-align: center;">{{< figure src="img/blogposts_2023/MoU_signature_20230306_02_2x1.jpg" caption="From left t Board (SOZA); [Dr James Edwards](https://music.dataobservatory.eu/authors/james_edwards/) Open Music Europe program direct Rado Kutaš, state secretary; Tomáš Mikš, SOZA; [Daniel Antal](https://reprex.nl/author/daniel-antal/), co-founder of Repre (https://music.dataobservatory.eu/authors/dominika_semanakova/)." numbered="false" >}}</td>

This cooperation is a very important milestone for our the Digital Music Observatory: our reproducible research will be us context in an EU member state. Our [Slovak Music Industry Report](https://music.dataobservatory.eu/publication/slovak_musi practice within the Slovak Republic.

We will create Live Policy Document on Music Economy, on Diversity and Circulation, on Music and Society, and on Music Inn We will contribute with automatically refreshed web resources and high-quality indicators about cultural and creative indu will be used to monitor the implementation of the "Cultural and Creative Industries Strategy of the Slovak Republic 2030" priemyslu Slovenskej republiky 2030)(https://www.culture.gov.sk/ministerstvo/strategia-kultury-a-kreativneho-priemyslu-2030

Figure 13.1: Screenshot on editing a webiste page.

The top part is using **YAML**:

YAML: **YAML Ain't Markup Language™**

What It Is: **YAML** is a human-friendly data serialization language for all programming languages.

It is a simple, machine-readable, but easily human-readable instruction for the computer about how to process the file.

Then, below the three - signs

Comes the text of the post. You can read in chapter [@\(#tidy-text\)](#) how to edit the post itself.

13.2 Automation

Our websites use hugo, an open-source static website creator system programmed in the (open-source) go language developed by Google. It is designed to develop websites that are easy to build, and work efficiently on the internet: they are easy to find and connect well with different web resources.

You can run hugo on Window, Mac, or Linux systems. hugo builds websites from standard file systems containing simple markdown texts, PNG/JPEG/WEBP images, with so called shortcodes. The **shortcodes** are repeating small tasks that are written in the go language to work fast and easy.

For example

```
{{< youtube w7Ft2ymGmfc >}}
```

embeds a YouTube video into a web page.

We use the [wowchemy](#) academic and research group templates. It is an awesome, free work that helps countless academic and researchers to make their work connect to other on the net. We pay a small donation to wowchemy, and they deserve your endorsement and donations, too.

The template was slightly modified (contextualized) by Reprex.

Our websites are built with the help of hugo from our standard file system (see 10), simply a GitHub repository (at [this](#) address.) So, our research website complies with the level 3 of the Open Policy Analysis Guidelines and the FAIR requirements.

You can “fork” the open source of our entire website, download it, and you can rebuild our entire website on our own computer, you can even modify it!

Figure 13.2: You can copy and download our entire website with source files and assets.

Each page (blogpost, event, author profile, info page) is made from a standard markdown file that you can modify with any word processor or text editor. Every page has a YAML header containing the page metadata for machine reading (what should be the title, subtitle, thumbnail image, etc.) If you want to suggest changes, make corrections, or write new content, you can do it with many different software tools.

Figure 13.3: We use *RStudio* from Posit, but you can use any editor.

We use *RStudio* from Posit, but you can use any editor. Technically you do not even need to be able to run hugo on your computer. However, without hugo you cannot visually check if your changes make sense.

If you run hugo on your computer, you can immediately check if your changes appear in the right place, form, and with the correct text. Then you can send these changes to our master folder, or repository with a pull request on GitHub. After approval, they will build on our server exactly the same way they were showing up on your computer if you tried it out with a locally running hugo server.

Figure 13.4: You can install *hugo* on any major computer operating system.

However, if you use *RStudio*, we recommend that you install it with `blogdown::install_hugo()`

Behind the scenes, from simple PNG-WEBP-JPEG files, and simple, tidy text, hugo (with the help of open source go language scripts) writes HTML, CSS, and Javascript coding to weave

your text and illustration into a website that is well connected to other web resources. While you could technically check every step under the hoods, you can also leave it as a black box and just think about it as an automated system that creates a website.

All aspects of our website are open source. You can re-use the engine, and the template, and you can reuse all the contents following the appropriate Creative Commons Licenses.

You can have an entire copy of our website templates, automation code, and the contents itself in your GitHub account, or in a downloaded (pulled) version on your computer. You cannot claim that you wrote it, and you must keep attributions to [wowchemy](#) (for the template), [Reprex](#) (for this actual setup), and each picture or text to its author. You should be particularly careful reusing the contributor partner logos, and you cannot make the impression that you represent them (unless, of course, if you do!).

13.3 Downloadable files

Figure 13.5: Static downloadable files in our website repository.

- We prefer PDF, pptx, docs, epub, xlsx files that were created by our own open source code because we know for certain what went into them (reproducibility and reviewability) and we can write so-called unit tests to search for frequent or typical mistakes.
- When we generate the PDF, pptx, docs, epub, xlsx or other files, we ensure that they contain the correct metadata for optimal findability, interoperability, and reusability.
- You can find/modify/place all downloadable files in the `static` subfolder of the website [source repository](#).

Commission, European, Directorate-General for Research, Innovation, L Baker, I Cristea, T Errington, K Jaško, et al. 2020. *Reproducibility of Scientific Results in the EU : Scoping Report*. Edited by W Lusoli. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/doi/10.2777/341654>.

Hoces de la Guardia, Fernando, Sean Grant, and Edward Miguel. 2020. "A framework for open policy analysis." *Science and Public Policy* 48 (2): 154–63.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scaa067>.

Open Music Europe. 2023a. "Repository: Report on Music Diversity and Circulation in Europe. GitHub." Open Policy Analysis Repository with Standardized File Structure. 2023.
<https://github.com/dataobservatory-eu/report-music-diversity-circulation-europe/>.

———. 2023b. "Report on Music Innovation & Technology in Europe. GitHub." Open Policy Analysis Repository with Standardized File Structure. March 25, 2023.
<https://github.com/dataobservatory-eu/report-music-innovation-technology>.

———. 2023c. "Repository: Report on Music, Society, and Citizenship in Europe. GitHub." Open Policy Analysis Repository with Standardized File Structure. March 25, 2023.
<https://github.com/dataobservatory-eu/report-music-society-citizenship>.

———. 2023d. "Repository: Report on the European Music Economy. GitHub." Open Policy Analysis Repository with Standardized File Structure. March 26, 2023.
<https://github.com/dataobservatory-eu/report-european-music-economy>.

———. 2023e. "Repository for the Contributors' Guidebook for the Data Observatories and Open Collections. GitHub." Open Policy Analysis Repository with Standardized File Structure. March 30, 2023. <https://github.com/dataobservatory-eu/report-music-innovation-technology>.

Philip, Kime, Wemheuer Moritz, and Lehman Philipp. 2023. *The biblatex Package. Programmable Bibliographies and Citations*.
<https://mirror.lyrahosting.com/CTAN/macros/latex/contrib/biblatex/doc/biblatex.pdf>.